

ADVANCES ON A VIRTUAL TESTING APPROACH OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES BASED ON MICROMECHANICS

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Keywords: Virtual testing, Laminated Composites, Multiscale

ABSTRACT

This work deals with the following question, which is central and crucial for the design of composite structures: how can one predict the evolution of damage up to—and including—final fracture? Such virtual testing, whose goal is to reduce drastically the huge number of industrial tests involved in current characterization procedures, constitutes one of today's main industrial challenges in the aerospace industry.

This work concerns our own modeling answer, and its derivation from today's understanding of the mechanisms of damage and their evolution on the micro, meso and macro scales. The proposed damage mesomodel—now used in a number of industrial codes—could be seen as the homogenized model of a micromechanics one; it includes a model of the interaction between delamination and ply microcracking which depends on some micromechanical material constants. However predictions could be much too much conservative for several cases as structures with sharp notches or structures involving important splits. Two lacks have been put forward. First, due to numerical constraints, computed splits, i.e. completely damaged zones due to matrix microcracking are too much thick. Second, present fiber failure criterion does depend on the stress gradient.

This work proposes solutions to the previous lacks of our virtual testing approach. A criterion is introduced for the detection of the split initiation in a ply and then the damaged zone is replaced by a cohesive interface parallel to the fiber, the height being the thickness of the ply. Regarding the fiber failure, thanks to a micromechanics analysis, the minimum volume to failure is no more a constant. The benefits that can be expected from these enhancements are illustrated on several test cases.

1 INTRODUCTION

The last quarter-century has witnessed considerable research efforts in the mechanics of composites in order to understand and predict the behavior of these materials, the ultimate goal being the design of the materials/structures/manufacturing processes. Even in the case of laminated composites, the prediction of the evolution of damage up to and including final fracture remains a major challenge which is at the heart of today's virtual structural testing' revolution engaged in by the aeronautical industry. Virtual structural testing consists, whenever possible, in replacing the numerous experimental tests used today by virtual tests.

An answer to the virtual structural testing challenge is what is called the “damage mesomodel for laminated composites”, developed at LMT-Cachan since the 1980s [1,5]. The main assumption is that the behavior of any laminate under any loading up to final fracture can be described using two elementary entities: the ply and the interface. It is derived from today's understanding of the mechanisms of damage and their evolution on the micro, meso and macroscales [1,2,4].

The damage mesomodel we proposed and which today is used in a number of industrial codes could be viewed as the homogenized version of a micromechanics model [1,4]. It includes a model of the interaction between delamination and ply microcracking that depends on some micromechanical material constants [3,7]. Today several similar mesoscopic approaches as [13] are being developed. Validation results could be found in [6,8,1].

However, the prediction from our mesomodel as others could be much too conservative in some cases, e.g. composite structures involving extensive splitting. Here, the mesomodel has been found to present a shortcoming: due to numerical constraints, the calculated splits, i.e. the completely damaged zones due to matrix microcracking, are too thick.

The paper deals with this challenge: the transverse microcracking and split modelling in the ply. Already several approaches have been proposed. A first approach is the high fidelity micromechanic model where every simple discontinuity in the plies and in the interfaces is described and therefore, one has to solve numerically a very large scale problem involving thousands of cracks. Even with high performance computational tools, such a micromechanic model leads to prohibitive computational efforts and, thus, is far from meeting the virtual structural testing requirements. However fundamentally, a split appears to be as a particular microcrack relatively isolated and mainly due to shear [4]

A part from purely microscopic and mesoscopic approaches, intermediate approaches have recently been proposed in the literature [9,10,11]. Classical cohesive interfaces are a priori introduced for transverse microcracking and combined with delamination interfaces. Two ways can be distinguished. The first one uses a priori experimental information about the cracking pattern (e.g. the position of the splits) and then is not a predictive approach. The second one considers a set of equally spaced potential cohesive interfaces in the different plies. To avoid prohibitive computations, the distance between two cohesive interfaces cannot be too small and then is not necessarily compatible with the micromechanics physics.

This question has led to interrogations related to the capability of “continuum damage mechanics” to reproduce splits. Some authors conclude with the absolute necessity to use discrete models. Our understanding is quite different. The difficulty to get “thin” splits with our mesomodel is only due to numerical problems associated to localisation phenomena involving very small time and space discretization. The mesomodel where microcracking is described by the microcracking density is correct; a split appears as a localisation phenomenon. The paper proposes a new approach able to simulate microcracking densities and splits. The main idea is to remind that until macrocrack initiation, continuum damage models and their numerical implementation do not involve any difficulty; localisation limiters are not active. So, one detects first the splits initiation and then one replaces it by a cohesive interface orthogonal to the ply (c.f. the ply thickness) and parallel to the fibres.

Apart one has a microcracking density all over the different plies. After given the fundamentals of the proposed approach, an illustration is developed in order to compare the classical mesomodel with the proposed approach. Comparison with experiments is also shown. To end, a word is given about the work in progress related to the enhancement of the fiber failure model.

2 THE MESOMODEL IN BRIEF

2.1 Generalities

This section gives a brief review of the damage mesomodel.

Figure 1: Composite structure considered as a 3D-assembly of plies and interfaces.

This model is based on two main assumptions:

- The behavior of any laminated structure can be reconstructed from the behavior of its two elementary constituents, the ply and the interface (see Figure 1);
- The damage state, which characterizes the elementary ply, is constant throughout a ply's thickness, but can vary between adjacent plies.

One should point out that in the mesomodel adjacent elementary plies having the same fiber direction are considered to form a single ply: in other words, no interface is defined between them. Starting from these assumptions, the constitutive behaviors of the ply and of the interface are defined in terms of a number of damage variables, taking into account different elementary damage scenarios (see Figure 2). For the ply:

- Diffuse intralaminar degradation related to phenomena occurring on the fiber's scale, such as fiber/matrix debonding or matrix rupture between fibers;
- Transverse matrix cracking caused by the percolation of diffuse damage into cracks parallel to the fibers which extend across the whole thickness of the ply;
- Fiber breakage;

and for the interface:

- Diffuse interface degradation related to small-scale cracking within the matrix-rich interface layer;
- Localized delamination caused by stress concentrations at the tips of the transverse matrix cracks.

Figure 2: The different damage internal variables.

One should note that while diffuse interlaminar and intralaminar damage occur on a scale which is much smaller than the ply's thickness, transverse cracking and localized delamination occur on a scale which is comparable to the mesoscale, and the corresponding damage variables have been derived based on micromechanical considerations.

In the following sections, we will review the main features of the enhanced mesomodel. The complete formulation of the ply and interface models can be found in the referenced works (in particular [5,7] for the enhanced ply model and [1] for the standard interface model).

2.2 Ply microcracking modeling

Microcracks follow diffuse damage through a percolation phenomenon. The internal variable is a continuous one: the microcrack density piecewise constant within the thickness of the composite. The associated damage force to the microcracking rate is given as follow using classical notations:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Y}_\rho = \frac{\partial E_d}{\partial A} = LH & \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{2E_2^0(1 - \bar{d}_{22})^2(1 - \tilde{d}')} - \frac{v_{23}^0}{E_2^0(1 - \bar{d}_{22})^2} \sigma_{33} \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+ \right] \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{22}}{\partial A} \\ & + LH \left[\frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{2G_{12}^0(1 - \bar{d}_{12})^2(1 - \tilde{d}')} \right] \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{12}}{\partial A} + LH \left[\frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{2G_{23}^0(1 - \bar{d}_{23})^2(1 - \tilde{d}_{23})} \right] \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{23}}{\partial A} \end{aligned}$$

Now, let us introduce the notations:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Y}_{22} &= H \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{2E_2^0(1 - \bar{d}_{22})^2(1 - \tilde{d}')} - \frac{v_{23}^0}{E_2^0(1 - \bar{d}_{22})^2} \sigma_{33} \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+ \right] \\ \bar{Y}_{12} &= H \left[\frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{2G_{12}^0(1 - \bar{d}_{12})^2(1 - \tilde{d}')} \right] \\ \bar{Y}_{23} &= H \left[\frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{2G_{23}^0(1 - \bar{d}_{23})^2(1 - \tilde{d}_{23})} \right] \end{aligned}$$

\bar{Y}_{22} , \bar{Y}_{12} and \bar{Y}_{23} are not strictly damage forces because the variables \bar{d}_{22} , \bar{d}_{12} and \bar{d}_{23} are not independent but relative to the underlying quantity ρ . They are distribution of the damage force \bar{Y}_ρ according to the modes.

Then, considering that $\rho = A/L$, the previous expression can be rewritten as:

$$\bar{Y}_\rho = \left[\bar{Y}_{22} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{22}}{\partial \rho} + \bar{Y}_{12} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{12}}{\partial \rho} + \bar{Y}_{23} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{23}}{\partial \rho} \right]$$

where G_I^c , G_{II}^c and G_{III}^c designate the critical energy recovery rates in Mode-I Mode-II Mode-III, respectively. The rupture envelope is then described by a classical mixed criterion of fracture mechanics. One has also:

$$\left[\left(\frac{\bar{Y}_{22} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{22}}{\partial \rho}}{G_I^c} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{\bar{Y}_{12} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{12}}{\partial \rho}}{G_{II}^c} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{\bar{Y}_{23} \frac{\partial \bar{d}_{23}}{\partial \rho}}{G_{III}^c} \right)^\alpha \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} = 1$$

Finally this leads to the following evolution of microcracking:

- if $\rho \leq \rho_s$

$$\rho = \sup_{\tau \leq t} \left[g \left\{ (\gamma_I \bar{Y}_{22})^\alpha + (\gamma_{II} \bar{Y}_{12})^\alpha + (\gamma_{III} \bar{Y}_{23})^\alpha \right\}^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \right]$$

$$\bar{d}_{22} = f_{22}(\rho), \bar{d}_{12} = f_{12}(\rho) \text{ and } \bar{d}_{23} = f_{23}(\rho); \gamma_I = \frac{1}{G_I^c}, \gamma_{II} = \frac{\frac{\partial f_{12}}{\partial \rho}}{G_{II}^c \frac{\partial f_{22}}{\partial \rho}}, \gamma_{III} = \frac{\frac{\partial f_{23}}{\partial \rho}}{G_{III}^c \frac{\partial f_{22}}{\partial \rho}}$$

$$g: x \rightarrow \frac{\partial f_{22}}{\partial \rho}^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{x} \right)$$

- otherwise

$$\rho = \rho_s; \bar{d}_{22} = f_{22}(\rho_s); \bar{d}_{12} = f_{12}(\rho_s); \bar{d}_{23} = f_{23}(\rho_s);$$

Functions $[\bar{d}_{22} \rightarrow \rho]$, $[\bar{d}_{12} \rightarrow \rho]$ and $[\bar{d}_{23} \rightarrow \rho]$ are obtain through the homogenization of the layer problem which defines the micro-meso relations.

2.3 Coupling microcracking/delamination

The enhanced mesomodel enables to couple the transverse matrix microcracking to the local delamination. Interface damage variables are linked to the density of cracks of the two adjacent plies. We introduce the free energy (per surface unit):

$$2e_{d,int} = \frac{\sigma_{33}^2}{K_3^0(1 - [\sigma_3]^+ d_I)} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{K_{12}^0(1 - d_{II})} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{K_{12}^0(1 - d_{III})} + \frac{\omega}{K_{12}^0} \sigma_{13} \sigma_{23}$$

with: $\omega(\rho, \rho')$, $d_{II} = \omega(d_I, \rho, \rho')$, $d_{III} = \omega(d_I, \rho, \rho')$. We distinguished two phases first the density of cracks increases until a threshold ρ_s then is constant:

- Interface damage evolution (Part 1):

$$\begin{cases} d_I = \frac{\langle \bar{Y}_{int} - Y_{0,int} \rangle_+}{Y_{c,int} - Y_{0,int}} & \text{if } d_I < 1 \\ d_I = d_{II} = d_{III} = 1 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

- Interface damage evolution (Part 2): with $g(\sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12}) = \frac{1}{Q_c} [\sigma_{22}^2 + \gamma \sigma_{12}^2]$,
If $g(\sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12}) < 1$ and $g'(\sigma_{22}', \sigma_{12}') < 1$, then no additional delamination.
else: $d_I = d_{II} = d_{III} = 1$

3 MICROCRACKING AND SPLITS

3.1 Damage physics

Splits are not related to a new damage mechanism: they are particular microcracks easily obtained thanks to a micromechanics model. Figure 3 show some experimental results coming from [4] and the micromechanics model from [1]. One can see that damage physics is well reproduced.

Figure 3: Microcracks in plies and interface (simulation and experiments).

Let us consider now simulations with the mesomodel which is the homogenized model of our micromechanics one. Splits appear as localized zone with high microcracking density. Their thickness depends on the chosen values of the parameters of the used localisation limiters. Practically, such values are quite far to physical ones and consequently the simulated split thickness is very large compared to the observed one for quasistatic loadings. Therefore, the mesomodel could lead to coarse fits with experiments for some cases where singularities occur. However, the computed split direction is parallel to the fibers and then correct. Let us also note that shear stresses dominate over the split zone. Figure 4 shows the thickness lack of the simulated split with the mesomodel.

Figure 4: Split simulated with the mesomodel.

3.2 The new approach

Let us note first that crack initiation does not depend on localisation limiters and then classical damage models are working perfectly until this initiation point. So, we characterize the split initiation by the two following criteria:

$$\rho \geq 0.2 \quad \rho_{III} \geq 0.75\rho_{\text{shear}}$$

Figure 5: Detection map of splits.

Once the split initiation detected in a ply, one replaces the damaged zone by a cohesive crack parallel to the ply fibers, the height being the thickness of the ply. Let us note that we continue to prescribe that the damage state is constant over the ply thickness but not of course over the composite thickness.

4 SINGULARITIES AND FIBER FRACTURE

The mesomodel includes fiber failure for which the parameter values of the used localisation limiters could play an important role which can be seen in Figure 6 for a DCB test. Both damage model with delay effect (characteristic time: τ) and damage gradient model (characteristic length: l) are used.

Figure 6: Influence of the localization parameters.

Here, we focus on the enhancement of the prediction of the initiation of fiber failure in the case of singularities that could be catastrophic. A first way is to calibrate the localisation parameters that means that one identifies a numerical model. Other ways are in progress.

5 CONCLUSION

Most of the calculations have been performed with the mesomodel implemented in SAMCEF. In progress, is the fiber fracture modelling at the fiber scale and its impact on the mesomodel

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Agence Nationale pour la Recherche as part of project ANR-12-RMNP-0001-05: Validation Expérimentale et Modélisation des StructuRes ComposiTEs sous Sollicitations CompleXes (VERTEX).

REFERENCES

- [1] Ladevèze P., Multiscale computational damage modelling of laminated composites. In: Sadowski T, editor. Multiscale Modelling of Damage and Fracture Processes in Composite Materials. CISM Courses and Lectures 474. New York-Springer (2005).
- [2] Ladevèze P Mechanics of the 21st Century; chap. A bridge between the micro- and mesomechanics of laminates fantasy or reality? Springer, Dordrecht, pp 187–201 (2005).

- [3] Ladevèze P., Lubineau G., Marsal D., Towards a bridge between the micro- and mesomechanics of delamination for laminated composites. *Composites Science and Technology* 66(6):698-712 (2006).
- [4] Violeau D, Ladevèze P, Lubineau G, Micromodel-based simulations for laminated composites. *Composite Sci Technol* 69(9):1364–1371 (2009).
- [5] Lubineau et P. Ladevèze, Construction of a micromechanics-based intralaminar mesomodel, and illustration in ABAQUS/Standard, *Computational Materials Science*, 43:137-145 (2008).
- [6] Daghia F, Ladevèze P Identification and validation of an enhanced mesomodel for laminated composites within the WWFE-III. *J Composite Mater* 47(20-21): 2675-2693 (2013).
- [7] Ladevèze P., Daghia F., Abisset E., Le Mauff C., A micromechanics-based interface mesomodel for virtual testing of laminated composites, *Advanced Modelling and Simulation in Engineering Sciences*, Springer Journal (2013).
- [8] Abisset E., Daghia F., Ladevèze P., On the validation of a damage mesomodel for laminated composites by means of open-hole tensile tests on quasi-isotropic laminates. *Composite Part A* 42:1515–1524 (2011).
- [9] Hallett SR, Jiang WG, Khan B, Wisnom MRModelling the interaction between matrix cracks and delamination damage in scaled quasi-isotropic specimens. *Composite Sci Technol* 68(1):80–89 (2008).
- [10] Bouvet C, Castanié B, Bizeul M, Barrau J-J Low velocity impact modelling in laminate composite panels with discrete interface elements. *Int J Solids Struct* 46(14–15):2809–2821 (2009).
- [11] Van der Meer FP, Sluys LJ, Mesh-independent modeling of both distributed and discrete matrix cracking in interaction with delamination in composites. *Eng Fracture Mech* 77(4):719–735 (2010).
- [12] Leguillon D., Strength or toughness? A criterion for crack onset at a notch, *European Journal of Mechanics A/Solids* 21:61-72 (2002).
- [13] Catalanotti G.,Arteiro A.,Hayati M.and Camanho P. Determination of the mode I crack resistance of polymer composites using the size-effect law, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* 118 :49-65 (2014).